

MEDICAL SCIENCES

ENVIRONMENTAL ANALYSIS IN HEALTH INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract

Many environmental factors can have a more or less impact on many organizations, including health institutions. Most importantly, these environmental factors are used to evaluate what form health institutions will have in the future. Since environmental factors have a considerable effect on structure and performance of health institutions, they must regularly and consistently conduct environmental analysis and develop evidence-based and implementable strategies grounded on the data obtained from these analyses.

The ability of health institutions to sustain their operations and achieve their definite goals depends on the analysis of internal and external environmental forces forming their positions in the sector. Therefore, the purpose of internal and external analysis is to gain a perspective on the opportunities and threats facing health institutions. Of course, the assessment of the findings gained from such an analysis must be used to develop strategies that will enable health institutions to stay ahead of their competitors.

In this study, we aim to identify major threats and opportunities for health institutions. We employ environmental analysis process to properly uncover these environmental threats and opportunities.

Keywords: Environmental Analysis, Environmental Analysis Process

Introduction

The analysis of factors in the internal and external environment of health institutions within the scope of strategic decision process is crucial for the efficiency and sustainability of their operations, and the achievement of a lasting place in the sector.

For health institutions, environmental analysis is an effective way to create a state of preparedness for not only environmental threats but also opportunities through identifying their strengths and weaknesses. From this perspective, it is vital for health institutions to develop strategies that are compatible with the environmental conditions and can be internalized with the structural characteristics of health institutions in order to sustain their operations in a dynamic and competitive environment.

The environment in which health institutions operate is dynamic and constantly changing. Therefore, health institution managers try to analyze environmental changes and developments regularly and continuously. That is, health institution managers develop shielding strategies to avoid threats from the external environment in order to benefit from opportunities arising from these changes and developments in the environment. One can argue that health institution managers conducting environmental analysis are one step ahead of those managers not conducting similar analysis by obtaining advance signs of potential threats and opportunities. However, the strategies developed through environmental analysis must be evidence-based and implementable to generate intended results.

To be explicit, health institutions are required to constantly monitor the economic, social, epidemiological, technological, and legal environmental conditions they face, gather information about environmental changes, and make strategic decisions based on this in-

formation. The process of compiling and evaluating information about environmental factors is called environmental analysis.

Purpose of the study

The purpose of environmental analysis is to identify threats and opportunities that may affect health institutions. Therefore, the aim of this study is to examine what environmental analysis implies for health institutions and how it can be used to develop evidence-based and implementable strategies to position them properly against environmental threats and have them to benefit from opportunities. If a health institution is unable to develop evidence-based implementable strategies, sometimes one or a few environmental factors can pose a critical threat to the institution and may have a critical negative impact on its ability to sustain its operation in the market. On the other hand, by developing evidence-based and implementable strategies against these environmental factors, health institutions can position themselves suitably in the future and can even be one step ahead of their competitors by taking better advantage of environmental opportunities.

Another aim of the study is to shed light on how environmental uncertainties facing health institutions can be reduced through employing the environmental analysis process accurately.

Methodology

In accordance with the purpose of the study, we conduct a detailed and systematic review of the related literature on environmental uncertainties facing health institutions, environmental analysis, and environmental analysis process. We provide a general assessment of the main findings of the literature regarding how effectively managing the environmental analysis process can be used to reduce environmental uncertainties for health institutions.

In the first step of the study, we examine the environmental factors from a general viewpoint, and how these environmental factors are incorporated into the process of environmental analysis. In the second step, we provide recent examples and discuss the environmental analysis process from the perspective of health institutions in detail.

Environmental analysis: opportunities and threats

Environmental analysis is a process of collecting and evaluating information about the environment in which institutions operate. That is, the main aim of the environmental analysis process is to gather information about environmental threats and opportunities. Environmental threats can simply be described as conditions with the potential to negatively affect the functions and performance of the health institution. Environmental opportunities, on the other hand, are a combination of conditions that facilitate the operations of the health institution, enable its growth, and enhance its performance. Factors surrounding health institutions create both threats and opportunities.

The followings are examples of environmental threats for the health institutions:

- Intensified competition, the emergence of new and strong competitors, and the growth of rival health institutions (economic environment),
- The Social Security Institution (SSI) setting lower service prices (legal environment),
- Increases in contribution shares (legal environment),
- Rising foreign exchange rates (economic environment),
- The government imposing additional restrictions on physician employment (legal environment),
- Changes in the expectations and health service utilization behaviors of the public (socio-cultural environment),
- The risk of emerging an economic crisis (economic environment),
- Rising inflation and increases in input costs (economic environment),
- Political instability (political environment),
- Rival health institutions starting to use new and capital-intensive medical technologies (technological environment and economic environment),
- Cooperation among rival health institutions and inadequate antitrust legislations hindering cooperation (competition and legal environment),
- Health personnel shortage (government policies, social environment),
- The possibility for international health institutions entering domestic health sector (international environment, economic environment),
- Decreasing burden of disease, declining incidence, and prevalence of diseases (epidemiological environment), and
- Declining regional and insured population (social environment).

As mentioned above, the external environment presents not only threats but also opportunities. Constructive changes in environmental factors can facilitate the attainment of performance goals such as growth, efficiency, and service quality for health institutions. Some examples of environmental opportunities are:

- Progress towards economic stability (economic environment),
- Increasing in the frequency of the public seeking health services (socio-cultural environment),
- Reduction in the procedures (such as referral requirements) limiting the use of health services by the public (legal environment),
- Development of new cost-effective service delivery models (technological environment),
- Input prices remaining stable or showing a tendency to decline (economic environment),
- Diminishing competition (economic environment),
- Implementation new measures to raise the supply of physicians and health personnel (political environment),
- Expansion in opportunities for collaboration with other health institutions (economic and legal environment),
- Boost in government incentives (political environment, economic environment),
- Enabling public-private partnerships (political environment, legal environment),
- Rise in healthcare literacy (social-cultural environment), and
- SSI implementing measures to bring service prices to reasonable levels (legal environment, economic environment).

Definitions of environmental threats and opportunities may not be the same for every healthcare institution. For example, if SSI lowers the service prices, while it is a threat for private healthcare with agreements with SSI, it may be an opportunity for the institutions without such agreements. Technological advancements in healthcare may be an opportunity for some health institutions because these advancements help them gain a competitive advantage. On the other hand, for health institutions which do not have access to new technologies for various reasons, technological advancement can be a serious threat. Healthcare institutions with sufficient financial and physical capital resources can put a large amount of investment into new technologies, but institutions lacking these resources to carry out this kind of investment may lose their competitive strength.

It is important to point out that health institutions may put different weights on threats and opportunities. Furthermore, the importance that managers at different health institutions assigning to threats and opportunities may vary. For example, an increase in input prices is a threat for all health institutions. However, the importance of this threat may not be the same for a small and a large hospital. Large hospitals may be able to achieve significant price advantages, that is, they may be purchasing their inputs at lower prices through bulk purchases. However, this cost saving arising out of

economies of scale is not possible for small hospitals making small-scale input purchases. Therefore, increases in input prices will have a more negative impact on small hospitals than large ones. In this case, small hospitals may try to work in partnership with other (small) hospitals and opt for bulk purchasing.

Environmental analysis process

Environmental analysis enables health institutions to avert negative shocks by providing information about environmental developments. Through the environmental analysis process, managers become aware of environmental factors and the dynamics of change in environmental factors, which also reduces the degree of environmental uncertainty. Managers having sufficient and reliable information about environmental factors and environmental change can make more effective decisions and develop the most appropriate strategies for the health institution. The primary aim of the environmental analysis process is to develop appropriate strategies. However, the environmental analysis process also has specific objectives. The specific objectives of environmental analysis process are (Swayne et al., 2006: 58):

- Identify and classify potential developments and problems in the external environment,

- Identify current developments that may affect the health institution in the future,
- Detect early warning signs of problems that might arise from environmental changes,
- Generate ideas about issues and developments that may impact the health institution,
- Produce information necessary for the health institution’s internal environmental analysis, specifying its mission, vision, values, and strategies, and
- Promote the spread of strategic thinking skills throughout the health institution.

The environmental analysis process is not a managerial activity with a start and end date. Because the external environment constantly changes, the environmental analysis process is a perpetual process, that is, it must be reconducted constantly. As presented in Figure 1, the environmental analysis process includes four basic stages. The stages of environmental analysis process are (Duncan et al., 2006: 68-69; Longest, 2004: 41-44; Henry, 2011: 41-42):

1. Scanning
2. Monitoring
3. Forecasting
4. Assessing

Figure 1. Environmental Analysis Process

Scanning Stage

During the scanning stage, the first signals of technological, political, economic, legal, and social developments in the external environment are detected. However, data gathered at this stage is generally imprecise, incomplete, and seemingly unrelated (Hitt et al., 2011: 40). In the health sector where environmental change is rapid, the scanning stage is of critical importance. Hence, health institutions which have the means to observe the signals of emerging developments and changes can have the opportunity to better prepare for the future. Health institution managers should not only monitor environmental factors directly related to health institutions (task environment) but also the general environment. For instance, although laser technology was developed in other industries, it began to be used in the health sector almost instantly. This kind of transition of developments between sectors is called environmental slip (Swayne et al., 2006: 70).

In the environmental scanning stage, subscription-based tools such as media tracking systems and internet-based scanning systems can be used. In Turkey,

companies such as Interpress, Medyatakıp, Ajanspress, and PRNet follow international, national, and sectoral developments and report them to their subscribers. Thus, managers can quickly become aware of current developments in the areas they are interested in.

Monitoring Stage

In the monitoring stage, health institution managers focus closely on initial signals of the environmental changes observed during the scanning stage, trying to determine the strength, continuity (trend), and potential effects of the changes on the health institution. For example, a hospital manager can gauge from a government spokesperson’s statement, “We will try to reduce health expenditures”, that the government will attempt to limit or lower service prices (Scanning stage). Based on this statement by the government, the hospital manager may start to investigate whether the SSI and the Ministry of Treasury and Finance are working on this issue (Monitoring stage). In the monitoring stage, the scattered, incomplete, and inadequate information obtained from the signals received in the scanning stage

is combined to form a meaningful whole. In the monitoring stage, managers organize the data collected from various data sources in their environmental database. Some examples of useful data sources for health institutions are:

- Publications of the Ministry of Health (for example, Health Statistics),
- Publications of the Turkish Statistical Institute (such as Health Statistics, Population Statistics, and Employment Statistics),
- Publications of professional organizations (such as the publications of Turkish Medical Association, and Turkish Pharmacists Association),
- Statistics and publications of Chambers of Commerce (for example, Medical Devices Sector Report),
- Associations' publications (such as the publications of Pharmaceutical Manufacturers Association, Medical Equipment and Device Manufacturers Association, and Turkish Pharmaceutical Industry Association),
- Publications of unions (such as the publications of the Revolutionary Health Workers Union, and Pharmaceutical Industry Employers Union),
 - Central Bank statistics (for example, Economic Indicators),
 - Academic and scientific publications,
 - International statistics (for example, World Health Organization's statistics),
 - Publications of the Higher Education Council (for example, Health Human Resource Reports), and
 - Reports and publications of other ministries.

While many signals are considered in the monitoring stage, the focus is more on specific environmental factors and environmental developments during the scanning stage. It should be noted that the managers begin to see the threats and opportunities that environmental developments pose for the health institution in the monitoring stage. Managers of health institutions working in a simple and stable environment may have complete information about the potential consequences of environmental developments, while managers of health institutions working in a dynamic environment must give greater importance to the scanning and monitoring stages to reduce uncertainties. Only with effective scanning and monitoring activity can the environmental uncertainty be significantly reduced. However, in a dynamic environment it is not possible to eliminate uncertainty completely (Longest, 2011: 44). Based on the trends identified in the monitoring stage, managers can decide what needs to be done (strategic objectives) and how it should be done (strategies) to prepare the health institution for the future (mission and vision).

Forecasting Stage

The scanning and monitoring stages are concerned with identifying developments in the external environment over a specific period. On the other hand, in the forecasting stage, managers form predictions for future developments using the data obtained in the scanning and monitoring stages. That is, in the forecasting stage, managers try to predict how the emerging develop-

ments will progress in the future, what kind of outcomes they will generate, and how these outcomes will affect the health institution. In today's rapidly changing environment most businesses give more importance to strategic management and forecasting. As strategic management is the design of the future from today, there is a big need for forecasts about the future. However, the accuracy of the forecasts is of great importance for successful strategic management activities. Therefore, managers must choose proper forecasting methods.

Evaluation Stage

The final stage of the environmental analysis process is the evaluation stage, which focuses more on judgments and interpretations rather than numerical data. In the evaluation stage, information about environmental developments generated in the scanning, monitoring, and forecasting stages is interpreted. That is, the main purpose of the evaluation stage is to go beyond the data and information to produce original ideas. It should be noted that these ideas are based on the judgments of the strategic management team conducting the evaluation (Longest, 2011: 45). Managers must have strategic thinking skills to be able to successfully complete the environmental evaluation. Strategic thinking refers to a future-oriented and development-oriented perspective (Zuckerman, 2006). According to Liedtka (1998; 2001), there are five basic characteristics of strategic thinking:

1. **Focus on Goals:** Shaping the future of the institution by focusing on the long-term goals and objectives of the institution.
2. **Opportunistic Intelligence:** Recognizing opportunities before they arise.
3. **Systemic Perspective:** Being able to see the institution as a whole and analyze the institution's relationships with the environment.
4. **Time-Oriented Thinking:** Making connections between the past, present, and future.
5. **Hypothesis-Oriented Thinking:** Being able to think scientifically, test new ideas, and learn from past experiences.

Conclusion

We can argue that the health institutions performing environmental analysis are able form a much faster feedback system than the ones not doing such an analysis. A feedback system enables health institutions to develop implementable and evidence-based strategies to respond to environmental threats and take advantage of environmental opportunities.

Environmental analysis facilitates health institutions to achieve their goals and makes their operations sustainable. On the other hand, it may not be possible to determine all the opportunities and threats arising in the environment around health institutions through environmental analysis. However, the more opportunities and threats detected by way of environmental analysis, the more strategies that are compatible with and applicable to these opportunities and threats can be developed, making environmental uncertainties manageable.

Mounting social needs and expectations, rising pressure from the SSI and private insurance companies,

increasing cost of services provided by health institutions, and the escalating competition in the health sector all contribute to the growing importance of environmental analysis.

Environmental threats facing health institutions can be classified as i) threats arising from economic environment such as the growth of rival health institutions, emergence of new health institutions, and appreciation of foreign exchange rates, ii) threats arising from legal environment such as SSI's policy of low service prices and increasing copays, iii) threats arising from political environment such as political instability, iv) threats arising from international environment such as the potential entry of international health institutions into the country, and v) threats arising from social environment such as the decrease in regional and insured population. On the other hand, we can categorize environmental opportunities for health institutions as i) opportunities resulting from economic environment such as economic stability, ii) opportunities resulting from socio-cultural environment such as a rise in the frequency of the community's access to health services, iii) opportunities generated in the technological environment such as the development of cost-saving medical kit, and iv) opportunities created in political environment-legal environment such as regulations facilitating public-private cooperation.

Environmental analysis for health institutions is not a one-time-only managerial activity, but rather a continuously renewed process as the environment

around healthcare institutions changes constantly. Environmental analysis process in the health sector involves scanning, monitoring, forecasting, and evaluation stages.

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